

EFFECT OF USEFULNESS, PERCEIVED EASE-OF-USE PRACTICES ON CONSUMERS' CHOICE OF TELECOMMUNICATION FIRMS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14170882s>

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of usefulness, perceived ease-of-use practices on consumers' choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: evaluate the effect of perceived usefulness on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria and Examine the effect of perceived ease-of-use on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The study adopted the survey research design. The sample size of the study was three hundred and eight four (384). The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The study hypotheses were tested with correlation methods. The findings showed that: perceived usefulness had a significant positive effect on consumers' choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r = 51.210$, $p_v = .000 < 0.05$) and perceived ease-of-use had a significant positive effect on consumers' choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r = .880$, $p_v = .000 < 0.05$). Based on findings, the study concluded that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use had significant positive effect on consumers' choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. Based on findings, the study recommended that management of telecommunication firms should ensure that their product meet the needs of consumers by giving a good quality services and features and management of telecommunication firms should also ensure that the brand of telecommunication they market are easy to use. Product-use instructions on the label should be easy to understand and followed by consumers. Customers should clearly understand how to determine the quantity of telecommunication to use in each wash situation.

KEYWORDS

Consumer choice,
Telecommunication, Enugu firm

INTRODUCTION

Continuously change or advancement in technology has grown world businesses as an instrument of growth across different economic boundaries and exposition and dispositions of consumers' choice products. Nevynda and Endy (2024) opines that the rapid growth in the digital world and technology has changed how individuals make purchases and transactions worldwide. Technological advances have changed how individuals make

purchases and transactions worldwide. Customers are no longer just conducting transactions with merchants in a conventional, direct manner. Due to technological advancements, customers can carry out faster, more convenient, and secure transactions without having to meet face-to-face with merchants in stores (Nevynda & Endy, 2024).

The technology advancement influence on people around the world has made slight changes to their behavior and attitudes. Because of the technology advancement, consumer choice of telecommunication to use emerged, which affects the lives of ordinary citizens (Miah, Hossain, Shikder, Saha, & Neger, 2022). Usefulness and perceived ease-of-use are most important features of the technological era that has led to a greater shift of consumers to online buying towards excommunication facilities (Omotayo & Omotope, 2018). As a result, with help of the technological era industry will continue to grow and evolve, resulting in more adoption of digital customer penetration.

However, Africa has witnessed a tremendous growth in technological advancement, with Nigeria having a growth rate of 25% per annum (Chinedu & Obot, 2019). Nigeria has experienced a significant shift in consumer behavioural choice over the past decade, largely due to the rise of technology. The convenience of being able to purchase products from the comfort of their homes or offices has made technological system buying the preferred option for many Nigerians. This shift has revolutionised the Nigerian retail landscape, opening up new opportunities for consumers and businesses. Nigeria is one of Africa's largest consumer markets. The market is projected to increase by 25.5 percent in 2023, contributing to the worldwide growth rate of 17.0 percent in 2023 (Folayan 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Although there are a lot of studies conducted in the context of usefulness and perceived ease-of-use, few studies investigated the usefulness and perceived ease-of-use of consumers' choice in Nigeria telecommunication firms. Most of the researchers investigated their purchase choice rather than their purchasing behavior which is the last stage of the buying process. To address this problem, researchers have conducted some studies on effect of usefulness, perceived ease-of-use practices on consumers' choice, the results of the studies showed mixed findings which necessitate the need for the introduction of a moderator. Nevertheless, there is still lack of studies on how usefulness, perceived ease-of-use practices affect consumers' choice, as research on Nigerian is scarce.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the effect of "usefulness, perceived ease-of-use practices on consumer choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria". The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Evaluate the effect of perceived usefulness on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the effect of perceived ease-of-use on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Perceived usefulness attributes of a detergent product refers to ability of the powder detergents to give a bright and clean wash, remove stain on cloths and facilitate heavy duty washing (Bajpai and Tyagi, 2017).

Perceived ease –of - use attributes of a detergent brand refers to consumer's believability of user instructions and ability to understand and follow the users instructions embodied in the powder detergent label.

Consumer Choice

Scholars contend that a consumer choice is made after a series of steps that often begins with recognition of a need or problem that warrant product purchases, followed by search for information about the product (either from marketing communications, previous stored information from memory or friend’s recommendations), then followed by critical evaluation of the brands qualities (brand alternatives) called the evoked set and making a choice from among the alternatives (Hiu, *et al*, 2017).

Conceptual Framework

As a result, the researcher’s conceptual framework was formulated based on these consistent attributes. Diagrammatically, the synthesized conceptual framework is presented and discussed below.

Figure 2.1 Proposed modified conceptual model between usefulness, perceived ease-of-use and consumers’ choice. Source: Tan and Teo, 2019.

Theoretical Framework

The theories of which paper was underpinning are technological acceptance model and choice theory of consumers’ choice.

Technological Acceptance Mode

Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) model was developed by Davis in 1986. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a hypothesis developed to determine how the system's PU and PEOU practically effects a person's behavioral choice over the telecommunication products (Davis, 1986). PU shows how the system increases system users' performance whereas PEOU highlights how the system does not demand too much effort to use, (Omotayo & Mayowa, 2018; Wang, 2017). In the context of telecommunication products are simple to use and deliver helpful information to their customers, their purchasing intent and behavior improves (Isa & Lajuni, 2020).

Choice Theory

Choice Theory was developed by William Glasser, a renowned American psychologist and psychiatrist. He theorized that behavior is a choice made by an individual, based on his or her feelings and needs, and is therefore not determined or controlled by external circumstances. In other words, the power lies within each person to determine how he or she will respond to the demands of the social and physical environment. Humans thus should not be perceived as victims or slaves of circumstances, but as self-determining beings who take responsibility for the consequences of their choices.

How Choice Theory is Related to the Present Study: although brand information can be communicational to consumers through marketing communications (advertising personal selling, publicity, public relations and direct marketing), recommendations by friends and past personal experiences they had with the brand; but the final choice of whether to buy or not to buy the brand depends on the consumer in the question. Consumers have the freedom to make brand choice of detergent they want from the list of available alternatives depending on their perception about the brand or how they feels that such brand will satisfy their washing needs based on the attributes possessed by the brand. These satisfying attributes are linked to those earlier discussed in this study.

Empirical Review

In this section, past related studies were reviewed in line with the objectives of the study.

Umanah and Braimoh (2017) study was to determine oral hygiene practices among university students; establish any association between oral hygiene practices and socio-demographic variables and find out the factors that may influence the choice of oral hygiene products in this group. Logistic regression analysis shows that the relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants and their frequency of tooth cleaning was statistically significant.

Musava (2017) examined the effect of perceived usefulness, corporate brand image and quality on consumer choice of washing powder detergents in Nyayo estate, Nairobi County. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Primary data was utilized. Primary data was collected using a semi-structured questionnaire. The respondents were residents of Nyayo Estate, Nairobi County. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. The study finding revealed that to a very great extent detergent quality such as meeting cleaning needs had the greatest influence on consumer choice for a detergent.

Iweka and Ederewhevbe (2018) examined the influence of rice quality on the choice of local rice in South East Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine the influence of rice quality on the choice of local rice in Nigeria. A sample of 400 respondents was elicited from a finite population of household rice consumers' resident in the five (5) South East Nigeria using a stratified random sampling and purposive non probability sampling techniques. Of this number, 366 copies were usable. Findings indicate that perceived quality of local influences consumers' choice of local rice.

Makhitha, Scheers and Mogashoa (2019) questioned which consumer attributes influence South African consumers to shop online. The population for the study was SA consumers who have internet access. A convenience sampling method was used to reach 104 respondents in SA. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 24. Various statistical analysis such as descriptive statistics, factor analysis and ANOVA were used. The findings of the study revealed that consumer's attributes such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and security have an influence on their online shopping behaviour.

Ibitoye (2020) investigated those attributes and factors that are likely to influence the brand choice of detergent consumers; study was on consumer choice criteria for detergent brands in Port Harcourt. The findings that emerged from the data analysis revealed that among the seven product attributes listed, perceived usefulness, foaming and lathering effect were found to be dominant in influencing the brand choice of detergent; and that demographic variable such as sex, age, and education do not influence brand choice with respect to the foaming of the brands.

Nevynda and Endy (2024) examined effects of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use for driving purchase intention in Nigeria. The purpose of this research was to look at how several factors, including quantity, quality of arguments, source credibility, perceived usability and utility, attitude toward buying, attitude toward brands, and intention to buy, affect Generation Z. Perceived usefulness and ease of use were not shown to be positively and significantly related in this study's hypothesis results. Attitude toward the purchase is positively and significantly impacted by perceived utility. Additionally, there is a favorable and statistically significant correlation between buy attitude and brand attitude, according to the data analysis.

Gap in Empirical Review

None of similar study has been carried out on local products in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The consumers preference for domestic products was investigated in Ghana by Damso-Abbeam, Armed and Boidoo (2014) and Ekiti State by Basorum (2008).The factors influencing consumers attitude towards local products in Ondo State was investigated by Alfred and Adekayode (2004). There is no study that systematically investigated the usefulness and perceived ease-of-use that influence consumers' choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria, thus creating several research gaps.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted survey design. The researcher used primary source of data which was gathered through the use of questionnaire. The population of this study was infinite due to the researcher cannot ascertain total number of customers who patronize three selected telecommunication firms namely MTN, Glo and Airtel in Enugu metropolis. The sample size was 384. In this study, simple random sampling was employed because it's a method in which each element of the population has an equal chance of been selected in the sample. The reason for selecting this method is because simple random sampling can be used in a homogenous population and has the least bias and has the most generalizability as each and every element can fall within the sample. This study employs the use of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 for data coding, data screening, and other preliminary analyses. However, for the major analysis, the study employed Multiple Regression Analysis for testing hypothesis.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Step One: Restatement of hypothesis in null and alternate form thus:

H₀₁: Perceived usefulness have no significant positive effect on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Perceived usefulness have significant positive effect on consumer's choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value < 0.05. Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

Table 1 ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Equation 1	Regression	402.674	1	402.674	51.210	.000
	Residual	.000	363	.000		
	Total	402.674	364			

Table 1 provides the effect of usefulness on consumers’ choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The results indicated that usefulness have a significant positive effect on consumer’s choice. From the evidence of this result, $F= 51.210$ and $pv = .000$. Thus we accept alternate hypothesis of H_{a1} which postulated that there was a significant positive effect of usefulness on consumer’s choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Step One: Restatement of hypothesis in null and alternate form thus:

H₀₂: Perceived ease-of-use have no significant positive relationship with consumer’s choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: Perceived ease-of-use have significant positive relationship with consumer’s choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the sign of the coefficient is negative and probability value < 0.05 . Otherwise, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate accordingly.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Equation 1 Regression	402.674	1	402.674	22.067	.000
Residual	.000	363	.000		
Total	402.674	364			

Table 2 provides the effect of perceived ease-of-use on consumers’ choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. The results indicated that usefulness have a significant positive effect on consumer’s choice. From the evidence of this result, $F= 22.067$ and $pv = .000$. Thus we accept alternate hypothesis of H_{a1} which postulated that there was a significant positive effect of perceived ease-of-use on consumer’s choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

After data analysis and test of hypotheses, we discovered that:

1. Perceived usefulness had a significant positive effect on consumers’ choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r = 51.210$, $pv = .000 < 0.05$).
2. Perceived ease-of-use had a significant positive effect on consumers’ choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria ($r =.880$, $pv = .000 < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on summary of findings, the researcher concluded that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use had significant positive effect on consumers’ choice of telecommunication firms in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In the light of study findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Management of telecommunication firms should ensure that their product meet the needs of consumers by giving a good quality services and features.
2. Management of telecommunication firms should also ensure that the brand of telecommunication they market are easy to use. Product-use instructions on the label should be easy to understand and followed by

consumers. Customers should clearly understand how to determine the quantity of telecommunication to use in each wash situation.

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